

CHALLENGES INVOLVING THE APPLICATION OF DISCONTINUOUS REINFORCED ALUMINUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES IN UNIFIED LIFE CYCLE ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

Discontinuous reinforced aluminum (DRA) metal matrix composites represent a promising class of advanced composites with potential use in unified life cycle engineering (ULCE). The employment of DRA in ULCE, however, presents many new challenges for nondestructive evaluation (NDE) and reliability. Fatigue failure in DRA is governed by a very large number of microcracks which contribute to instability at unusually small crack sizes. As a result, difficulties are encountered when conventional NDE and fracture mechanics-based prediction techniques are applied. Nevertheless, this report will detail a strategy on how DRA can be used in ULCE if the microcrack distributions at various stages in fatigue are known.

I. INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous reinforced aluminum (DRA) metal matrix composites have received significant attention in the past decade due to the opportunity to tailor them to achieve physical properties not possible with unreinforced aluminum [1]. As a result, a wealth of information has been published on DRA (e.g. [2-6]), mainly on improvements in stiffness, strength-to-weight ratio, wear and fatigue resistance, and thermal expansivity. When compared with other advanced materials such as continuous reinforced composites, DRA offer the additional benefits of lower processing costs since many existing techniques for manufacturing Al alloys can be carried over for their production. All of these characteristics together make DRA attractive candidates for a number of aerospace, automotive, and recreational products.

DRA are just beginning to be introduced into applications that may require unified life cycle engineering (ULCE). For example, they have been used for aircraft structures such as the vertical tail stabilizer of the U. S. Air Force F-22 fighter [7] and the escape hatch for C-141 transports [8]. Before DRA can play a more prominent role in ULCE, however, several major issues must be addressed. Among these is their propensity for catastrophic failure in fatigue at unusually small critical crack sizes due to their reduced ductility. In studies by the authors and others on 2xxx Al alloys reinforced with SiC whiskers [9-13], fatigue failure can occur without the appearance of a stably growing fatal crack detectable by nondestructive evaluation (NDE), i.e. 200 μm , as typically observed in conventional metals. Instead, failure is governed by the nucleation and growth of a very large number of distributed surface microcracks* which do not exceed a crack length of 100 μm for most of the fatigue life (Fig. 1). This high density of microcracks leads to widespread crack coalescence and ultimately the formation of the fatal crack. In some instances, the effective critical crack size as measured from the fracture surface

is just 200 μm [11]. The expected critical crack size, on the other hand, as calculated from the linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) fracture toughness value ($K_{1c} = 12.7 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for a 2124 Al-SiC_w composite [16]) is 1.2 mm.

Figure 1. Surface fatigue microcracks in a 2124 Al-SiC_w composite at a) $N/N_f = 0.33$ and b) $N/N_f = 0.95$. Arrow indicates loading direction. $R = -1$, $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 500 \text{ MPa}$, $N_f = 13,718$ cycles.

The objective of this report, therefore, is to specify the precise requirements for NDE detection and fracture mechanics-based prediction techniques in order to allow not only DRA, but also other advanced materials with similar fatigue characteristics, to be applied safely in ULCE. More accurate, cost effective quality assurance inspections are always desired given evidence that available predictive and NDE methods are still not fully capable of treating crack growth processes that occur in service [17]. With the introduction of DRA and other advanced materials into ULCE applications, even more rigorous mechanisms of crack growth must be modeled. To set the standards for DRA composites, a cumulative experimental-theoretical-applied approach to ULCE is presented in this study. Experimental data on distributions of surface fatigue microcracks in smooth specimens of a 2124 Al-20 vol.% SiC_w composite serve as the basis for this philosophy. The tool used for the reliability predictions is a simple Monte Carlo simulation being developed as a part of an actual ULCE project [18]. This simulation allows the timing and needed sensitivity for the NDE inspections to be determined. Efforts in NDE are also made in this work and are directed at tracking changes in the eddy current impedance caused by increasing amounts of microcracking from continued cyclic loadings.

* Crack sizes will be distinguished by a terminology similar to Reference 14. Microcracks refer to mechanically- and microstructurally-small cracks less than 100 μm in length and depth, and of sizes comparable to their own crack tip plastic zones. Short cracks are physically-small cracks 100 to 500 μm in either directions. Long cracks have lengths and depths which are greater than 500 μm and have growths which can be described by the Paris equation [15].

II. FATIGUE AND NDE OF DRA COMPOSITES

Studies by the authors [9-13,19] have shown the significant effects of microcracks on the fatigue failure of a 2124 Al-SiC_w composite. These works have primarily tracked microcracks at different stages in fatigue using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses of replicas of the specimen surfaces (e.g. Fig. 1). Four major fatigue processes are seen for this composite: microcrack initiation, growth, arrest, and coalescence. An increasing number of newly initiated microcracks, mostly from fractured and debonded SiC whiskers and whisker clusters, nucleates over time. In-depth observations show that these microcracks initiate and grow preferentially in arrays that maximize the energy release rate [12]. Microcracks can grow on their own and/or by linking with other microcracks nearby (i.e. coalescence). Most microcracks, however,

remain small and appear to arrest immediately after initiating. Others grow for some period and then arrest. The high density of microcracks present makes linkages inevitable. Near the end of life, the interaction of some microcracks brings about large increases in their stress intensities leading to coalescence and the fatal crack formation. The effective critical crack lengths and depths, as measured from the fracture surface, vary from just 68 to 250 μm and 20 to 140 μm , respectively; both for applied maximum stresses (σ_{max}) of 600 to 400 MPa [11]. The longest crack observed on the replicas near the end of life is typically less than 60 μm in length. Given the above critical crack length range, this corresponds to the linkage(s) of just 2 to 5 large microcracks. The brief interval between the last replica and failure suggests that instability takes place almost immediately afterwards. Little time was spent in fatal crack growth. With regard to the NDE of DRA, this implies that crack detection capabilities will need to be on the scale of *tens of microns* to avoid the possibility of catastrophic failure since a stably-growing, detectable crack of 200 μm may never appear.

Given the enormous difficulties of detecting small microcracks individually by NDE, particularly outside of controlled laboratory conditions, one approach being examined for DRA and similar materials is to track changes in materials properties and/or NDE signal responses due to the increasing density of microcracks. Work has been performed in related studies to assess this route using primarily eddy currents on smooth fatigue specimens of a X2080 Al-SiC_p composite [20]. Simultaneous microcrack density and eddy current measurements, utilizing replicas and an automated eddy current measurement system [21], respectively, were made. Results show that extremely small changes in the signal impedance (up to 2%) can be detected and followed. The specimens with the greatest amounts of microcracking clearly exhibited the highest variations in impedance. In-situ eddy current measurements using a commercial portable eddy current unit were also tried with the specimens loaded in the testing machine to open the cracks. This commercial unit, however, was not accurate enough to detect the extremely small changes in impedance found with the automated system.

III. MICROCRACK GROWTH IN DRA AND RELIABILITY PREDICTIONS

Before microcrack growth behavior in DRA can be characterized, some background on the use LEFM in conventional prediction methods is necessary. Fracture mechanics is particularly useful making fatigue crack growth rate (da/dN) predictions to estimate the remaining life of a structure to schedule inspections. The Paris equation [15] is most commonly employed for these calculations. It can describe crack growth in the linear region of the sigmoidal log-log scaled da/dN versus stress intensity factor (ΔK) relation for long cracks in monolithic metals and some composites (Fig. 2). The Paris equation, however, tends to overestimate da/dN for lower values of ΔK approaching long crack growth threshold (ΔK_{th}) where long cracks do not grow since their local crack tip stress intensities are too small [22]. Still, the Paris equation is often extended into and beyond "thresholded" regime to make short and microcrack da/dN predictions (dashed line in Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Schematic of long crack growth behavior in metals and some composites.

Figure 3. Individual microcrack growth behavior in the 2124 Al-SiC_w composite.

The practice of extending the long crack Paris curve to microcracks is controversial. It is well known that microcracks can deviate greatly in da/dN from those predicted for long cracks in the exact same material. Short cracks can and do grow below ΔK_{th} , typically at rates faster than long cracks at the same ΔK [22-26]. Similitude between short and long cracks also does not exist [22]. Since a majority of the life of a crack is spent as a short crack in the "thresholded regime", extrapolating the Paris equation to make reliability predictions could be particularly dangerous as catastrophic failure could occur while within the expected component service life. Attempts to account for these Paris equation differences in expected da/dN through the use of modified versions of ΔK or ΔJ (the elastic-plastic method) have yielded only mixed results. For example, when ΔK is modified into an *effective* stress intensity factor (ΔK_{eff}) to account for crack closure effects, one study found that the growth rates converged [27] while another still observed significant variations [28]. This lack of agreement may be due to the use of ΔK itself since small scale yielding does not hold for short cracks or to the semiempirical nature of its modified versions. Expressions for the crack driving force (e.g. ΔK) are also based only on the remote loading stress/strain field and do not take into account microstructurally-induced factors which greatly influence microcrack growth [29]. Microcracks exist in an environment of varying elastic moduli and short-range residual stresses, thus a probabilistic approach to crack growth rate predictions may be more appropriate than a deterministic one [14]. In materials where failure takes place by the linkages of distributed microcracks, a probabilistic approach may be the only alternative [17].

To assess the Paris equation method for microcracks in the DRA, individual microcracks were followed on sequences of replicas with the SEM to obtain the crack growth rates. From the micrographs, changes in the crack length (b) over time (in number of fatigue cycles, N) were measured. The growth rates along the surface crack length, db/dN , were found by curve-fitting the b versus N data and differentiating the best-fitting curve. The obtained db/dN were then matched with ΔK for semi-elliptical cracks [30]. Examples of the results are shown in Fig. 3. There were large scatters in the db/dN of individual microcracks not seen in long crack growth. Coalescence and arrest occurred frequently in the growth of some microcracks leading to periods of accelerated or little/no growth, respectively. The entire growth spectrum could not be fitted empirically to a single Paris equation relationship if each data point was strictly followed. Some microcracks did exhibit a linear growth curve on the log db/dN versus log ΔK plots, but they were very few in number. The growth rates of most individual microcracks simply cannot be fitted closely using the deterministic Paris equation as with long cracks.

Figure 4 shows the microcrack growth rates obtained in this work for the 2124 Al-SiC_w composite as compared with those found in the literature for long cracks in similar 2124 Al-SiC_w composites and an unreinforced 2124 matrix using compact tension (CT) specimens [31,32]. Microcrack growth rates were higher than those of long cracks at the same ΔK for low values of ΔK approaching ΔK_{th} for long cracks in the composites. The opposite was seen at larger values of ΔK . The smaller slopes for the microcracks may be interpreted as reflecting the ability of DRA to resist the growth of large microcracks better than long cracks. This is most likely due to the crack trapping ability of the reinforcement on microcracks. When the cracks are long, the crack tip stress intensity is large enough to allow them to propagate directly through the whiskers by fracturing them. It is noted that the crack growth rate data typically used in reliability are taken from CT specimens even though cracks of these lengths (on the order of several mm) may never appear (as seen for DRA). Furthermore, basing predictions on the growth rates of long cracks can underestimate the actual sizes of cracks present, thus allow for the possibility that a component being used contains a critical-sized crack.

IV. MICROCRACK DISTRIBUTIONS AND THE ULCE OF DRA

To account for these shortcomings in NDE detection and LEFM crack growth rate prediction capabilities due to microcracks, a novel reliability philosophy is proposed here to allow DRA to be used in ULCE. The basis for this strategy revolves around the evolution of microcrack length distributions (MLD). The probability of an NDE-detectable crack appearing depends on the population of undetectable microcracks. By knowing how and at what rate these microcracks grow in fatigue, the rate of emergence of detectable cracks can be estimated to assist in scheduling the inspections. Distributed microcracking occurs in the fatigue of almost all structural materials, whether at room or high temperature conditions in air or corrosive

environments. Consequently, the reliability model described here for DRA should also be valid for other materials, such as a 304 stainless steel [9]. Information on MLD was primarily gathered from the studied 2124 Al-SiC_w composite since the high density of microcracks present allows statistical adequate numbers of microcracks to be more easily counted.

Figure 4. Microcrack growth behavior in the 2124 Al-SiC_w composite compared with long crack growth data in similar composites and matrices obtained from CT specimens.

Figure 5. Schematic of projected crack size distribution as obtained by growing EIFSD with Paris equation using random parameters.

Before the rationales for this methodology can be understood, some basic assumptions taken in current reliability theory must be explained. A recent paper on aircraft reliability describes a stochastic approach to durability prediction being developed by the U. S. Air Force for aging aircraft [33]. This model is based on identifying an Equivalent Initial Flaw Size Distribution (EIFSD), usually represented by a fictitious distribution (e.g. the lognormal distribution), for a structural element by cycling the element and measuring the time it takes for cracks to reach a reference size. These data are then used to "grow the distribution of cracks backward" to obtain the EIFSD by means of a Paris equation-type growth containing random variables (Fig. 5). To calculate the crack size distribution at any point in service life, the EIFSD is then grown forward by the same rule. In this method, the crack density is essentially taken to be constant.

To test the idea of using fictitious distributions, experimental data on MLD in the 2124 Al-SiC_w composite were obtained by measuring the lengths of all microcracks in a designated area on the replicas at different stages in the fatigue life. The MLD at a σ_{max} of 500 MPa showed over 420 microcracks in an area of 0.1 mm² after 80% of the fatigue life (normalized number of fatigue cycles, $N/N_f = 0.80$) [10]. At 550 MPa, nearly 500 microcracks were present after $N/N_f = 0.67$ (Fig. 6). Attempts were made to fit these MLD with standard distribution functions. Among these, the lognormal distribution (LD) gave the best fit [10]. This fit, however, became poor late in the fatigue life and did not always satisfy χ^2 statistical goodness of fit tests at a confidence level of 95%. The LD tends toward the exponential distribution at values of length above the mode [19]. While the exponential nature of the LD allows it to fit the smallest crack lengths, more cracks in the (upper) tail actually exist than would be predicted by it. Since this is the portion of the MLD bearing the crack lengths of greatest importance to failure, the poor overall fits of common distribution functions suggest that using them to represent a population of cracks, although convenient, can be inaccurate.

The rate of change in the crack density represents the difference between the rates of nucleation and of coalescence (Fig. 7). Although these plots are roughly linear, a marked increase in coalescence with additional cyclic loadings requires that the rate of nucleation also increase to compensate for reductions in the number of cracks as a result of linkages. The effects of this can be visualized by considering that, if Paris equation coefficients are randomly distributed as suggested by Reference 33, the probability of a given group of small, undetectable cracks giving rise to a significant detectable or dangerous macrocrack increases with the actual number of microcracks waiting in that group. Since the total number of microcracks increases with time, one should expect that, even if all units having detectable cracks are excluded, the

probability of failure per unit time will still increase for those remaining because the growth of a detectable crack is a rare event while the nucleation of a microcrack is not.

Figure 6. Microcrack length distributions in the 2124 Al-SiC_w composite (area = 0.1 mm²).

Figure 7. Rate of initiation of microcracks in the 2124 Al-SiC_w composite.

The reason for concern over cracks that do not exist is that they cannot be extracted out by inspection. A repair action, using the terminology of Reference 33, may include replacement or merely assurance by inspection that no cracks below a certain size exist apart from those which are overlooked. Consequently, unless the repair action results in the actual replacement of a member, the evolution of the microcrack distribution goes unchecked. Since, both the rate of new cracks appearing in the MLD and the rate of detectable cracks emerging out of it are increasing functions of time, it is reasonable to assume that the hazard function for an old but crack-free structural member is not going to be the same as that for a relatively new one. Yet, in common with many textbooks and papers, Reference 33 shows graphs indicating that after inspection the hazard function behaves similarly to that for a new part. The consequence of this is that inspection intervals tend to be equispaced for a constant risk.

A discussion indicating that the characteristics of actual MLD lead to conditions requiring inspections to be closer together as the structure ages in order to keep the risk constant was presented in Reference 34. This study shows that the rate of appearance of NDE-detectable cracks from evolving MLD is not consistent with the notion of an EIFSD (unless the distribution first evolves by microcrack processes before a Paris-type growth is applied to it). Microcracks obey a Paris equation only some of the time when they are growing [19]. Otherwise microstructural arrest and coalescence dominate leading to intermittent crack growth. In the microcrack regime, the effect of length (hence ΔK) on growth velocity is too weak to allow a Paris growth description since microcracks do not experience the same thresholds as larger cracks do. Long cracks couple many microstructural domains together and average the local thresholds. Local thresholds vary widely and naturally occurring microcracks only grow where conditions favor them. The pattern of periods of arrest has stronger effects on microcrack growth than does their ΔK . Together, these facts suggest that the only way an EIFSD would be realistic is if it was obtained at the end of life. Since predictions are based on a fixed initial distribution and Paris-type growth, at times before the end of life the durability model of Reference 33 would predict the presence of cracks of particular lengths that in reality would not exist due to the effects of arrest and coalescence in retarding or accelerating crack growth, respectively. As cracks reach an NDE-detectable size, they begin to obey a Paris growth law. This relationship, however, is still subject to some variability and needs a stochastic description when considered for reliability. In addition, new smallest-experimentally discernible microcracks appear over time with a nearly fractal character as the magnification is increased. The net result is a tendency for NDE-detectable cracks to appear at increasing rates with additional fatigue. The apparent initial growth speed of these late-appearing cracks may be quite high since they often emerge from coalescence. Therefore, to keep up with these late-appearing cracks, inspection intervals need to be shortened as the structure ages.

To demonstrate how MLD may actually be used for scheduling reliability inspections in ULCE, a Monte Carlo simulation was applied [9,19]. A Monte Carlo simulation was chosen specifically for this purpose since it represents a step toward describing the MLD and

microcrack growth as Markov processes. Markov processes are important in the modeling for finding simple closed-form expressions which can describe the entire crack distributions. The simulation considers the four major fatigue processes for DRA mentioned in Section II (i.e. initiation, growth, arrest, coalescence). The crack growth law is taken as the Paris equation in the present calculation *only* when the cracks do grow (i.e. not when the cracks are arrested or growing by coalescence). The simulation provides a mean of estimating the fraction of cracks of given lengths as a function of fatigue loading and number of cycles. This information is required for determining both the timing and sensitivity of the inspections.

The simulation results are shown in Fig. 8 as compared with the "best-fitting" LD and observed, experimental distributions at different stages of fatigue. Both the simulation and lognormal distributions agree reasonably well with the experimental data although they did not always satisfy χ^2 tests at a confidence level of 95% [19]. Considering the simple assumptions used, however, the simulation fits are quite good and even improve the LD fits most of the time, particularly late in life. The simulation can predict cracks at both ends of the MLD. It can closely fit both the exponential nature of the smallest microcracks, to which the LD is limited, and the upper tail of large microcracks. It is noted that the simulation also improves on the LD for MLD in a 304 stainless steel [9]. Thus, in principle, the simulation can be readily employed for materials in which distributed microcracking takes place.

Figure 8. Simulation of microcrack length distributions as compared with experimentally observed and lognormal distributions at a) $N/N_f = 0.58$ and b) $N/N_f = 0.95$.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Present-day ULCE methods rely on NDE to provide input on the crack size distributions in a fatigued component at any given period in the life. However, as shown in this report, the small sizes of microcracks in DRA composites for most of the fatigue life, as well as the lack of a detectable, stably-growing long fatal crack, severely limits the use of NDE if these materials are applied in ULCE. The detection capability required for finding individual cracks in DRA is on the scale of tens of microns, a size much too small to detect by conventional NDE methods except under well-controlled laboratory conditions. One possible approach being studied is to track the effects of a microcrack population, rather than individual ones, on materials properties and/or NDE signal responses. From work performed to date using primarily eddy currents, small, distinct changes in the signal impedance can be observed as a result of increasing amounts of fatigue microcracking. Thus, this approach represents a possible path to follow in enabling NDE to be utilized in the ULCE of DRA composites.

A new strategy for improving reliability predictions was also presented in this paper. This methodology demonstrates that it may be more feasible to have inspection times and sensitivities determined from the evolution of microcrack distributions. The main rationales for this are that present LEFM-based reliability theory cannot accurately describe microcrack growth, closely model crack populations with fictitious distributions, and account for increasing numbers of fatigue cracks being initiated into a structure as it ages. To avoid missing a significant crack, it will be necessary to incorporate all of these factors, particularly

late in the fatigue life where more frequent, shorter spaced inspections may be needed. The Monte Carlo simulation applied in this work illustrates how this MLD approach to inspection scheduling can be pursued to allow DRA to be accommodated in ULCE.

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REFERENCES

1. W. H. Hunt, Paper presented at the *Processing and Fabrication of Advanced Materials Symposium*, Materials Week '93, Pittsburgh, PA (1993).
2. C. Zweben, *Adv. Mater. Processes*, 145, 1, 28-30 (1994).
3. J. E. Allison and G. S. Cole, *J. Met.*, 45, 1, 19-24 (1993).
4. S. V. Nair et al., *Int. Metals Rev.*, 30, 6, 275-90 (1985).
5. D. R. Williams and M. E. Fine, in *Int. Conf. Compos. Mater., ICCM-5 Conf. Proc., 5th*, W. G. Harrigan, Jr. et al., eds., TMS-AIME, Warrendale, PA, 639-70 (1985).
6. J. J. Bonnen et al., *Metall. Trans.*, 22A, 1007-19 (1991).
7. F. J. Lavoie, *Mater. Eng.*, 9, 27-33 (1986).
8. M. O. Lavitt, *Aviat. Week Space Technol.*, 140, 3, 13 (1994).
9. E. Y. Chen et al., Paper presented at the *Fatigue Crack Initiation Symposium*, Materials Week '93, Pittsburgh, PA (1993).
10. E. Y. Chen et al., *Scr. Metall. Mater.*, 30, 6, 737-42 (1994).
11. M. Sasaki et al., *Metall. Mater. Trans.*, 25A (1994).
12. E. Y. Chen et al., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* (In press)
13. D. R. Williams, *Ph.D. Thesis*, Northwestern University, Evanston, IL (1985).
14. R. O. Ritchie and J. Lankford, in *Small Fatigue Cracks*, R. O. Ritchie and J. Lankford, eds., TMS-AIME, Warrendale, PA, 1-5 (1986).
15. P. C. Paris and F. Erdogan, *J. Basic Eng.*, 85D, 528-534 (1963).
16. L. Lawson et al., in *Mechanisms and Mechanics of Composites Fracture*, R. B. Bhagat et al., eds., ASM International, Materials Park, OH, 65-75 (1993).
17. M. F. Kanninen and C. H. Popelar, *Advanced Fracture Mechanics*, Oxford University Press, New York, NY, 60 (1985).
18. L. W. Schmerr and D. O. Thompson, in *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, 12, D. O. Thompson and D. E. Chimenti, eds., Plenum Press, New York, NY, 2325-31 (1993).
19. E. Y. Chen et al., *Metall. Mater. Trans.* (In press).
20. E. Y. Chen et al., Unpublished Research, Northwestern University (1995).
21. N. Nakagawa et al., in *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, 9, D. O. Thompson and D. E. Chimenti, eds., Plenum Press, New York, NY, 1065-72 (1990).
22. S. Suresh and R. O. Ritchie, *Int. Met. Rev.*, 29, 6, 445-76 (1984).
23. S. Pearson, *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, 7, 235-47 (1975).
24. M. Klesnil et al., *Scr. Metall. Mater.*, 18, 1231-34 (1984).
25. J. Lankford and D. L. Davidson, in *Small Fatigue Cracks*, 51-71.
26. J. Lankford, *Fatigue Fract. Eng. Mater. Struct.*, 5, 3, 233-48 (1982).
27. D. L. Davidson, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, 36, 2275-82 (1988).
28. G. Ebi and P. Neumann, *Mater. Technol.*, 10, 498-503 (1990).
29. S. J. Hudak and K. S. Chan, in *Small Fatigue Cracks*, 379-405.
30. Y. Murakami and M. Isida, *Trans. Japan Soc. Mech. Engrs.*, 51, 464, A, 1050-56 (1985).
31. W. A. Logsdon and P. K. Liaw, *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, 24, 5, 737-51 (1986).
32. T. Christman and S. Suresh, *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, A102, 211-16 (1988).
33. A. P. Berens et al., in *Structural Integrity of Aging Aircraft*, S. N. Althuri et al., eds., Springer, New York, NY, 37-51 (1991).
34. L. Lawson and E. Y. Chen, *Journal of Testing and Evaluation* (In press).